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Association between Nutritional Habits and Quality of Life of Health Sciences Students from Eight South-East European Countries

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Introduction: Starting university education often leads to changes in students' nutritional habits due to new responsibilities and environmental influences. Studies have shown that students generally do not maintain a proper diet, often skipping meals, particularly breakfast and consuming food that is high in energy but low in nutritional value, with high levels of saturated fats, trans-fatty acids, added sugars and salt. Unhealthy nutritional habits can lead to an imbalance between energy intake and expenditure, increasing the risk of overweight and obesity and the development of non-communicable diseases, which significantly decreases students' quality of life.

Aim: The aim of this study was to determine the association between nutritional habits and quality of life of health science students from South-East Europe.

Methods: The study was conducted in a form of a cross-sectional study between April and September 2023 on a sample of 3,473 students from 69 faculties in 8 countries (Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia, Serbia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, and Greece) using an online survey questionnaire.

Results: In the overall sample, 30.8% of students had a satisfactory level of adherence to proper nutrition, while 69.2% did not. None of the students had dietary habits fully aligned with recommendations for proper nutrition. Students from Greece had the highest percentage of satisfactory adherence to proper nutrition (40.5%), while students from Bosnia and Herzegovina had the lowest (20.3%) ($\chi^2=73.868$; $p<0.001$; $fi=0.146$). Nutrition students had the highest percentage (37.5%) of satisfactory adherence to proper nutrition, while pharmacy students had the lowest percentage (26.8%) ($\chi^2=17.87$; $p=0.007$; $fi=0.072$). Satisfactory adherence to proper nutrition was associated with significantly higher mean scores across all domains of quality of life, including self-rated quality of life ($t=-10.097$; $p<0.001$), health quality ($t=-7.632$; $p<0.001$), physical health ($t=-4.584$; $p<0.001$), psychological health ($t=-3.479$; $p<0.001$), social health ($t=-4.392$; $p<0.001$) and environmental health ($t=-5.054$; $p<0.001$), compared to unsatisfactory adherence to proper nutrition. Satisfactory adherence to proper nutrition was a statistically significant predictor of all domains of students' quality of life.

Conclusions: The results of this study can be used to plan various public health activities at the national, regional and international levels in order to improve student nutrition, thereby reducing the risk of developing non-communicable diseases and enhancing quality of life.

Keywords: nutritional habits; quality of life; medical students; public health; young adults; Western Balkans